

ISUAAAT15-012

A REDUCED-ORDER MODEL FOR COMPRESSIBLE FLOWS BASED ON AN EFFICIENT PROPER ORTHOGONAL DECOMPOSITION METHOD

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents a Reduced-Order Model (ROM) for compressible flows using an efficient Proper Orthogonal Decomposition (POD) method. To reduce the computational cost of the POD method, the governing equations were written as a function of the specific volume instead of density. This substitution allowed for pre-computation of the coefficients of the ordinary differential equations (ODEs) obtained by Galerkin projection. Consequently, the computational time of the POD method was significantly reduced. Several methods for enhancing stability of the ODE solver were explored: the penalty method for enforcing boundary conditions, artificial dissipation, and a new method that modifies the number of modes used in the POD approximation. The ROM was successfully validated for three cases: a quasi-one-dimensional nozzle, a two-dimensional channel flow, and an axisymmetric nozzle, for both on- and off-reference conditions. The computational time of the reduced-order model written as a function of specific volume was at least 10,000 times smaller than that of the full-order model.

INTRODUCTION

Advancements in computer hardware have led to the ability to solve complex flow problems using high fidelity methods. Unfortunately, the simulation of these full-order models (FOMs) is computationally expensive. A reduction of the run time of these FOMs can be achieved by

improving the numerical scheme and the grid quality. While these approaches may be effective, the FOM is still limited in its use for design, verification and validation of controls and structures, and for real-time feedback [1, 2]. A better approach to decrease computational cost is the use of model reduction techniques to produce Reduced-Order Models (ROMs). These model reduction procedures replace the large system of partial differential equations of the full-order model by a much smaller system of ordinary differential equations (ODEs) that makes up the reduced-order model. The Proper Orthogonal Decomposition (POD), developed by Karhunen and Loeve [3, 4] and applied to fluid dynamics by Lumley [5], is most commonly used to reduce the system of PDEs within the FOM. POD has successfully been used for turbomachinery applications [6], cavity flows [7], and multi-phase flows [8, 9, 10], among many others.

While POD is the more traditional method to use for model reduction, there are several other methods that have been examined and used to develop stable and/or accurate ROMs. Lucia *et al.* have presented an extensive review of the different model reduction techniques [11] including Volterra theory, harmonic balance, and the traditional POD method. Other methods include a genetic algorithm to minimize the residual of the POD approximation in the governing equations [12], a deflation method to compute basis functions sequentially with the solver to reduce errors from the eigenvalue problem [13], a dynamic mode decomposition [14], a bi-orthogonal decomposition [15], using Central Voronoi tessellations as the model reduction procedure [16], or a Balanced POD [17]. Manipulations to

the traditional POD have involved modifying the form of the governing equations, *e.g.*, linearizing the system or changing the inner product of the model reduction procedure. Acceleration techniques of the ROM have also been explored [18, 19].

The main benefit of a ROM is in its ability to be interpolated for off-reference conditions, that is, for conditions where the parameters of the governing equations have been changed. Several model reduction techniques listed above address different aspects of off-reference interpolation. Additionally, there have been further improvements in interpolating ROMs using a Grassmann manifold for aeroelastic problems [20, 21].

An unfortunate consequence of model reduction procedures is their inability to guarantee the preservation of the stability of the FOM. This greatly limits the robustness of the ROM for handling changes in geometry and flow parameters. Investigations into preserving the stability of the FOM or enforcing stability in the ROM have been performed. For example, extensions on the traditional POD method for stability have been done for linear-time invariant ROMs [22, 23] with other research focusing on eigenvalue reassignment of linear-time invariant systems [24]. It is possible to extend the eigenvalue reassignment of linear-time invariant systems to nonlinear systems through an iterative approach [25]. Another approach is to develop stability-preserving inner products respective to the type of flow problem [26, 27]. Boundary conditions are another option for enforcing stability in a ROM. These can be implemented in different ways, but one approach that has successfully been used is the penalty method [28, 29, 30]. This method enforces the boundary conditions by penalizing the ODEs for not satisfying the boundary conditions of the governing PDEs. Artificial dissipation has also been used successfully to stabilize ROMs after the fact by adding an artificial dissipation term to the governing equations [31, 32, 33].

This paper presents an efficient POD method that is based on the mass, momentum and energy conservation equations written as a function of the specific volume instead of density. This formulation allows for the pre-computation of the coefficients of the ODEs produced by the POD, which significantly reduces the computational time of this ROM compared to previous ROM implementations. The following section presents the governing equations of the full-order model written using specific volume in place of density. The POD-based reduced-order model is subsequently described. Results are then presented for a quasi-one-dimensional nozzle, a two-dimensional channel, and an axisymmetric nozzle.

NOMENCLATURE

Roman

A	Area
\tilde{A}	Outlet pressure amplitude
a	Time coefficient
c	Speed of sound
d	Space dimension, $d=1, 2$ or 3
J	Jacobian

m	Number of modes
N	Number of nodes
n	Number of modes for one variable
p	Pressure
\bar{p}	Mean outlet pressure
\mathbf{R}	Autocorrelation matrix
s	Entropy
u	x -Velocity
\mathbf{v}	Velocity vector
v	y -Velocity
w	z -Velocity
\mathbf{Z}	Zeta-variable state vector

Greek

γ	Ratio of specific heat capacities
ε	Relative error
ζ	Specific volume
ν^{diss}	Artificial dissipation parameter
τ	Penalty parameter
ϕ	Basis function
φ	Outlet pressure phase shift
$\tilde{\omega}$	Outlet pressure frequency [rad/sec]

Subscripts

out	Outlet value
ref	Reference value

METHODOLOGY

GOVERNING EQUATIONS

The Euler equations written using the specific volume ζ instead of the density ρ are

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial t} + \mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla \zeta - \zeta (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}) &= 0 \\ \frac{\partial \mathbf{v}}{\partial t} + \mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{v} + \zeta \nabla p &= 0 \\ \frac{\partial p}{\partial t} + \mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla p + \gamma p (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}) &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{v} = (u, v, w)^T$ is the velocity vector and p is pressure. For convenience, the governing equations written in vectorial form for any node i are

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{Z}_i}{\partial t} + \mathbf{A}_{1_i} \frac{\partial \mathbf{Z}_i}{\partial x} + \mathbf{A}_{2_i} \frac{\partial \mathbf{Z}_i}{\partial y} + \mathbf{A}_{3_i} \frac{\partial \mathbf{Z}_i}{\partial z} = 0 \quad (2)$$

where

$$\mathbf{Z}_i = [\zeta \quad u \quad v \quad w \quad p]_i^T$$

$$\mathbf{A}_{1_i} = \begin{bmatrix} u & -\zeta & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & u & 0 & 0 & \zeta \\ 0 & 0 & u & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & u & 0 \\ 0 & \gamma p & 0 & 0 & u \end{bmatrix}_i$$

$$\mathbf{A}_{2_i} = \begin{bmatrix} v & 0 & -\zeta & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & v & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & v & 0 & \zeta \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & v & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \gamma p & 0 & v \end{bmatrix}_i$$

$$\mathbf{A}_{3_i} = \begin{bmatrix} w & 0 & 0 & -\zeta & 0 \\ 0 & w & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & w & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & w & \zeta \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \gamma p & w \end{bmatrix}_i$$

\mathbf{Z}_i is called herein the zeta-variable state vector. This formulation of the governing equations is preferred to using conservative or primitive state vectors for developing the POD-based reduced-order model as shown in the following section.

REDUCED-ORDER MODEL BASED ON PROPER ORTHOGONAL DECOMPOSITION

Proper Orthogonal Decomposition, otherwise known as Principal Component Analysis or the Karhunen-Loeve Decomposition, is a procedure for extracting the optimal basis set from an ensemble of observations. The proper orthogonal decomposition is used in conjunction with the Galerkin projection to create reduced-order models. The idea is to project the full-order model onto an optimal subspace where the error between the full-order model and the projection is minimized.

Let us consider a set of discrete snapshots of a transient scalar function represented by $q(x, t_i)$, $i = 1, \dots, M$. These observations are assumed to form a linear, finite-dimensional Hilbert space L^2 on a spatial domain D . The observations $q(x, t_i)$ are parameterized by t_i which represents time. From the ensemble of observations, POD extracts time-independent orthogonal basis functions $\{\phi_k^q(\mathbf{x})\}$ and time-dependent orthogonal coefficients $\{a_k^q(t_i)\}$, such that the reconstruction

$$q(x, t_i) = \sum_{k=1}^m a_k^q(t_i) \phi_k^q(x), i = 1, \dots, M; m \leq M \quad (3)$$

is optimal in the sense that the averaged least-square truncation error

$$\varepsilon_m^q = \left\| \left\| q(x, t_i) - \sum_{k=1}^m a_k^q(t_i) \phi_k^q(x) \right\| \right\| \quad (4)$$

is a minimum for any given number $m \leq M$ of basis functions over all possible sets of basis functions [34].

Herein $\|\cdot\|$ denotes the L^2 -norm given by $\|f\| = (f, f)^{\frac{1}{2}}$, where (\cdot, \cdot) denotes the inner product. $\llbracket \cdot \rrbracket$ denotes an ensemble average over the number of observations $\llbracket f \rrbracket = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{i=1}^M f(x, t_i)$. The optimum condition specified by (4) reduces to [35, p. 89]

$$\int_D \llbracket q(x) q^*(y) \rrbracket \phi(y) dy = \lambda \phi(x) \quad (5)$$

which is a homogeneous Fredholm integral equation of the second kind [36, p. 97]. Therefore, the optimal basis functions $\{\phi_k^q(\mathbf{x})\}$, called the POD basis functions, are the eigenfunctions of the integral equation (5), whose kernel function is the autocorrelation function $\llbracket q(x) q^*(y) \rrbracket = R(x, y)$, where $*$ denotes complex conjugate.

For a finite-dimensional case, where the observations $\mathbf{q}(x, t_i) = [q(x_1, t_i), q(x_2, t_i), \dots, q(x_N, t_i)]^T$ are vector-

valued functions, the autocorrelation function $R(x, y)$ is replaced by the tensor product matrix

$$\mathbf{R} = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{i=1}^M \mathbf{q}(x, t_i) \mathbf{q}^T(y, t_i). \quad (6)$$

The matrix \mathbf{R} is a symmetric positive semidefinite matrix where the eigenvectors are orthonormal to each other [37].

The method of snapshots [38] is used herein to calculate the eigenvectors of \mathbf{R} . This method is efficient when the resolution of the spatial domain, N , is higher than the number of observations, M . Details of the implementation of the method of snapshots are presented in [34, 39].

Since $\phi_i^q(\mathbf{x})$ are orthogonal vectors, the time coefficients $a_i^q(t)$ can be calculated using (3) as

$$a_i^q(t) = \frac{(q(x, t), \phi_i^q(\mathbf{x}))}{\|\phi_i^q(\mathbf{x})\|^2}. \quad (7)$$

Although (7) produces the ‘‘exact’’ time coefficients, they cannot be used for predicting the solution at off-reference conditions, *i.e.*, conditions different from those predicted by the full-order model. For off-reference conditions, the time coefficients are computed by solving a system of ordinary differential equations, as shown in the following paragraphs.

The reduced-order model is developed using the basis functions extracted from snapshots of the data generated by the full-order model [40]. Each component of the state vector is approximated using a linear combination of the basis functions and time coefficients, as given in (3). This approximation is then substituted into the governing equations to convert a system of N PDEs into a system of m ODEs, where N is the total number of degrees of freedom and m is the total number of modes. Since the Euler equations are homogeneous functions of degree 2 [41, p. 377-8], the system of ODEs can be written as

$$\sum_{i=0}^{n^{q_k}} a_i^{q_k}(t) \phi_i^{q_k}(\mathbf{x}) = \mathcal{F}_k \left(\sum_{i=0}^{n^{q_l}} \sum_{j=0}^{n^{q_r}} a_i^{q_l}(t) a_j^{q_r}(t) \phi_i^{q_l}(\mathbf{x}) \phi_j^{q_r}(\mathbf{x}) \right), \quad g = 1, \dots, n^{q_k}, \quad k = 1, \dots, d + 2 \quad (8)$$

where q_k is the k -th variable of the state vector, n^{q_k} is the number of modes used to approximate the variable q_k , and d is the spatial dimension, $d \in [1, 3]$. The symbol $'$ denotes derivative with respect to one of the spatial coordinates. Variables q_l and q_r of function \mathcal{F}_k depend on k . For example, for $k = 1$, it results from (1) that \mathcal{F}_1 has six terms that include the following four pairs (q_l, q_r) : (u, ζ) , (v, ζ) , (w, ζ) , (ζ, u) , (ζ, v) , and (ζ, w) .

The approximated governing equations (8) are then projected along the basis functions of the variables of the left-hand side term of (8). Due to the fact that the basis functions $\phi_i^{q_k}(\mathbf{x})$ are orthonormal, the result of the Galerkin projection is

$$\dot{a}_g^{q_k}(t) = \mathcal{F}_k \left(\sum_{i=0}^{n^{q_l}} \sum_{j=0}^{n^{q_r}} a_i^{q_l}(t) a_j^{q_r}(t) \left(\phi_i^{q_l}(\mathbf{x}) \phi_j^{q_r}(\mathbf{x}) \phi_g^{q_k}(\mathbf{x}) \right) \right), \quad g = 1, \dots, n^{q_k}, \quad k = 1, \dots, d + 2. \quad (9)$$

It is advantageous if the inner product reflects the physics of the flow [26]. Therefore, the L^2 inner product was

selected herein since when used with the velocity variables it yields the rate of kinetic energy

$$(\dot{\mathbf{v}}, \mathbf{v}) = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \|\mathbf{v}\|^2.$$

The discrete L^2 inner product used in this model is

$$(f, g) = \int_{\Omega} f g d\Omega \approx \sum_{i=1}^N f(x_i) g(x_i) \Omega_i = \sum_{i=1}^N f(x_i) g(x_i)$$

where $\Omega \in \mathbb{R}^d$ is the reference spatial domain with unit length, width, and depth and \mathbf{x} is the discretized spatial coordinate with pointer i .

It should be noted that (9) is a nonlinear system of m ODEs, where $m = \sum_{k=1}^{d+2} n^{qk}$. It is also worth noting that in the method presented herein, the FOM discretized governing equations are not projected along the subspace directly, as was done in [10, 42], but rather the governing equations are projected along the subspace. Therefore, the discretization used for the ROM is different from that used for the FOM. This may lead to small errors between the FOM and the ROM [16]. The stability of the ROM is achieved through artificial dissipation, enforcement of the boundary conditions using the penalty method, and a new method that involves modifying the number of modes in the POD approximation.

STABILITY

The convergence of the ROM solution depends on the stability of the system of ODEs (9). Assessing the stability of a system revolves around capturing its response given a perturbation and seeing whether that perturbation gets damped out or grows over time. This response makes up the difference between a stable, neutrally stable, and unstable system. For example, consider a linear homogeneous ODE

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}} = \mathbf{A} \mathbf{x} \quad (10)$$

where \mathbf{A} is an $n \times n$ matrix and \mathbf{x} is a vector of length n . Assume that this system has a solution that exists and is unique. It can be shown that the solution to this problem is

$$\mathbf{x} = \sum_{j=1}^n C_j e^{\lambda_j t}$$

where C_j are arbitrary constants and λ_j are the eigenvalues of \mathbf{A} . If $\lambda > 0$ then \mathbf{x} grows to infinity as $t \rightarrow \infty$, and the system is unstable. Likewise, if $\lambda < 0$ then \mathbf{x} will decay to zero as $t \rightarrow \infty$, and the system is stable. Finally, if $\lambda = 0$ then the system remains at a steady state, and the system is neutrally stable.

The same procedure applies to nonlinear systems, but the system needs to be linearized about a fixed point. Linear stability analysis on nonlinear systems, however, will not provide information about bifurcation points, that is, where the system diverges into a stable or unstable solution. Nonetheless, linear stability analysis provides useful information on stability. Consider (9) written in vectorial form

$$\dot{\mathbf{a}} = \mathcal{F}(\mathbf{a}) \quad (11)$$

where $\mathbf{a} = (a_1^\zeta, \dots, a_{n^\zeta}^\zeta, a_1^u, \dots, a_{n^u}^u, \dots, a_{n^p}^p)^T$ is a vector of length m , which can also be written in condensed form as $\mathbf{a} = (a_i^{qk})^T, i \in [1, n^{qk}], k \in [1, d+2]$. $\mathcal{F}(\mathbf{a})$ is a nonlinear functional describing the dynamics of the ODE

system. The components of $\mathcal{F}(\mathbf{a})$ are $\mathcal{F}_k, k \in [1, d+2]$ where $\mathcal{F}_k \in \mathbb{R}^{n^{qk}}$. Equation (11) is linearized about a fixed point \mathbf{a}^* which is defined as the point where $\mathcal{F}(\mathbf{a}^*) = 0$. This is also known as the equilibrium point. The linearization about the equilibrium point yields

$$\mathcal{F}(\mathbf{a}) \approx \mathcal{F}(\mathbf{a}^*) + \mathbf{J}(\mathbf{a}^*)(\mathbf{a} - \mathbf{a}^*) \quad (12)$$

where $\mathbf{J}(\mathbf{a}^*)$ is the $m \times m$ Jacobian of the ODE system evaluated at the equilibrium point. If one defines $\mathbf{u} = \mathbf{a} - \mathbf{a}^*$ then (11) becomes $\dot{\mathbf{u}} = \mathbf{J}(\mathbf{a}^*) \mathbf{u}$. This equation looks similar to (10), and its stability is analyzed by evaluating the eigenvalues of the Jacobian $\mathbf{J}(\mathbf{a}^*)$. Herein, the Jacobian components are computed using a first-order finite difference method

$$J_{ij} = \partial \mathcal{F}(a_i^{qk}) / \partial a_j^{ql} \quad (13)$$

where $i \in [1, n^{qk}], j \in [1, n^{ql}], k, l \in [1, d+2]$.

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE BOUNDARY CONDITIONS

The full-order model solution satisfies the boundary conditions and therefore the POD-basis functions are expected to do the same. Although the boundary conditions are generally satisfied by the POD-basis functions, the time-dependent boundary conditions may not be adequately captured by the POD model. For this reason, the boundary conditions of the reduced-order model are implemented herein using the penalty method [28, 43].

Before presenting how the penalty method was applied for the reduced-order model, let us illustrate how it can be implemented for the full-order model. For the full-order model, the penalty method applied to the vectorial governing equations (1) written for all N nodes yields

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{Z}}{\partial t} + \mathbf{A}_1 \frac{\partial \mathbf{Z}}{\partial x} + \mathbf{A}_2 \frac{\partial \mathbf{Z}}{\partial y} + \mathbf{A}_3 \frac{\partial \mathbf{Z}}{\partial z} = -\boldsymbol{\tau}_z (\mathbf{Z}_{BC} - \mathbf{F}(t))$$

where $\mathbf{Z}, \mathbf{F} \in \mathbb{R}^{(d+2)N}$, $\mathbf{A}_1, \mathbf{A}_2, \mathbf{A}_3, \boldsymbol{\tau}_z \in \mathbb{R}^{(d+2)N \times (d+2)N}$. $\boldsymbol{\tau}_z$ is the penalty parameter diagonal matrix, \mathbf{Z}_{BC} is the value of \mathbf{Z} at the boundary location, and $\mathbf{F}(t)$ is a vector describing the time-dependent boundary conditions. For example, for a flow with an oscillating outlet static pressure boundary condition the only non-zero terms of $\text{diag}(\boldsymbol{\tau}_z)$ and \mathbf{Z}_{BC} will be those corresponding to pressure on the outlet grid points.

For the reduced-order model, the penalty method was implemented by adding to (11) the projection of the $\boldsymbol{\tau}(\mathbf{Z}_{BC} - \mathbf{F}(t))$ term on the basis function such that

$$\dot{\mathbf{a}} = \mathcal{F}(\mathbf{a}) - \boldsymbol{\tau}(\mathbf{Z}_{BC} - \mathbf{F}(t), \phi(\mathbf{x})) \quad (14)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\tau} \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$ is a diagonal matrix.

The time variation of pressure and specific volume were specified at the outlet boundary. Consequently, for $d = 3$, the forcing function corresponding to grid point i was

$$\mathbf{F}_i(t) = \left[(\gamma f(t))^{-\frac{1}{\gamma}}, 0, 0, 0, f(t) \right]^T.$$

The boundary condition term $(\gamma f(t))^{-\frac{1}{\gamma}}$ is an isentropic boundary condition enforced on the specific volume at the outlet. This boundary condition was not enforced in the full-order model but was added to the reduced-order model for stability. Its derivation is shown in Annex A.

Stability preserving bounds for the penalty parameter have been determined using an energy-based stability

analysis [28, 30]. This ensures that the real part of the eigenvalues of the system remains negative, that is, the energy in the system is decreasing. Assuming that $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ is constant across its entries, the ODE becomes

$$\dot{\mathbf{a}} = \mathcal{F}(\mathbf{a}) - \boldsymbol{\tau}\mathbf{K}$$

where \mathbf{K} is $(\mathbf{Z}_{BC} - \mathbf{F}(t), \phi(\mathbf{x}))$. Projecting along \mathbf{a} gives

$$(\dot{\mathbf{a}}, \mathbf{a}) = (\mathcal{F}(\mathbf{a}), \mathbf{a}) - \boldsymbol{\tau}(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{a})$$

where $(\dot{\mathbf{a}}, \mathbf{a})$ can be simplified to $\frac{1}{2}\frac{\partial}{\partial t}\|\mathbf{a}\|^2$, which represents the energy of the system. To remain stable, the energy must be decreasing, that is, $\frac{1}{2}\frac{\partial}{\partial t}\|\mathbf{a}\|^2 \leq 0$. This leads us to a stable value for $\boldsymbol{\tau}$

$$\boldsymbol{\tau} \geq \frac{(\mathcal{F}(\mathbf{a}), \mathbf{a})}{(\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{a})} \quad (15)$$

Alternately, by moving the $\mathcal{F}(\mathbf{a})$ term of (14) to the left-hand side, the penalty boundary term can be seen as the residual

$$\dot{\mathbf{a}} - \mathcal{F}(\mathbf{a}) = \mathbf{R}(\mathbf{a}, \boldsymbol{\tau}) = -\boldsymbol{\tau}\mathbf{K} \quad (16)$$

that should be driven to zero. This method does not guarantee stability, but will add to the accuracy of the solution.

ARTIFICIAL DISSIPATION

Artificial dissipation has been shown to stabilize POD-based reduced-order models [31, 32]. The artificial dissipation terms are added to the governing PDEs and projected along the respective optimal subspace. No artificial dissipation is applied to the mean (or zeroth) mode. The ODEs (11) are then rewritten as

$$\dot{\mathbf{a}} = \mathcal{F}(\mathbf{a}) + \boldsymbol{\nu}^{\text{diss}}\mathbf{S} \quad (17)$$

or in component form

$$\dot{a}_i^{qk} = \mathcal{F}_i + \nu_i^{\text{diss}} \sum_{j=1}^{n^{qk}} (\boldsymbol{\phi}_{j,xx}^{n^{qk}} + \boldsymbol{\phi}_{j,yy}^{n^{qk}} + \boldsymbol{\phi}_{j,zz}^{n^{qk}} + \boldsymbol{\phi}_i^{n^{qk}}) a_j^{n^{qk}} \quad (18)$$

where $i \in [1, n^{qk}]$, $k \in [1, d+2]$. \mathbf{S} consists of the projection of the second derivatives along the respective subspace and the artificial viscosity term $\nu_k^{\text{diss}} \geq 0$ is arbitrarily varied between equations depending on the stability and desired accuracy.

Values for ν_k^{diss} can also be calculated to guarantee system stability using the same energy-based method as before for $\boldsymbol{\tau}$. Assuming a penalty method has been put into place, the governing ODEs are

$$\dot{\mathbf{a}} = \mathcal{F}(\mathbf{a}) + \boldsymbol{\nu}^{\text{diss}}\mathbf{S} - \boldsymbol{\tau}\mathbf{K} \quad (19)$$

where \mathbf{K} is the same as defined before. Assuming $\boldsymbol{\nu}^{\text{diss}}$ is constant across its components and projecting along \mathbf{a} gives

$$(\dot{\mathbf{a}}, \mathbf{a}) = (\mathcal{F}(\mathbf{a}), \mathbf{a}) + \boldsymbol{\nu}^{\text{diss}}(\mathbf{S}, \mathbf{a}) - (\boldsymbol{\tau}\mathbf{K}, \mathbf{a})$$

where, again, $(\dot{\mathbf{a}}, \mathbf{a}) = \frac{1}{2}\frac{\partial}{\partial t}\|\mathbf{a}\|^2$ is used to create an equation for $\boldsymbol{\nu}^{\text{diss}}$ that will decrease system energy.

$$0 \leq \boldsymbol{\nu}^{\text{diss}} \leq \frac{(\boldsymbol{\tau}\mathbf{K} - \mathcal{F}(\mathbf{a}), \mathbf{a})}{(\mathbf{S}, \mathbf{a})} \quad (20)$$

MODIFIED NUMBER OF MODES

The eigenvalues of the Jacobian matrix evaluated at the critical points determine the stability of the ROM. These eigenvalues can be modified by changing the number of modes, n^ℓ . To illustrate this approach, let us expand $\partial\mathcal{F}(\mathbf{a}^\zeta)/\partial\mathbf{a}^u$ of the Jacobian in (13).

$$\frac{\partial\mathcal{F}(\mathbf{a}^\zeta)}{\partial\mathbf{a}^u} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial\mathcal{F}(a_1^\zeta)}{\partial a_1^u} & \frac{\partial\mathcal{F}(a_1^\zeta)}{\partial a_2^u} & \dots & \frac{\partial\mathcal{F}(a_1^\zeta)}{\partial a_{n^u}^u} \\ \frac{\partial\mathcal{F}(a_2^\zeta)}{\partial a_1^u} & \frac{\partial\mathcal{F}(a_2^\zeta)}{\partial a_2^u} & \dots & \frac{\partial\mathcal{F}(a_2^\zeta)}{\partial a_{n^u}^u} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \frac{\partial\mathcal{F}(a_{n^\zeta}^\zeta)}{\partial a_1^u} & \frac{\partial\mathcal{F}(a_{n^\zeta}^\zeta)}{\partial a_2^u} & \dots & \frac{\partial\mathcal{F}(a_{n^\zeta}^\zeta)}{\partial a_{n^u}^u} \end{bmatrix}$$

If the number of modes n^u is reduced by one, then the terms of the last column of $\partial\mathcal{F}(\mathbf{a}^\zeta)/\partial\mathbf{a}^u$ are all zero. Consequently, the eigenvalues of the Jacobian will change. Per experience, the only restriction for this method is that the number of modes for a variable cannot be modified when on its respective equation. For example, the conservation of mass equation must use n^ζ number of modes, but all other variable modes can be changed. This technique proved to be helpful for modifying the eigenvalues of the Jacobian to obtain a stable numerical method for solving the system of ODEs, as shown in the following section.

RESULTS

QUASI-ONE-DIMENSIONAL NOZZLE FLOW

The quasi-one-dimensional nozzle was selected as an initial validation case of the reduced-order model. The full-order model was given by the Euler equations written in characteristic form [44]

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial s}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial s}{\partial x} &= 0 \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(u + \frac{2c}{\gamma-1} \right) + (u+c) \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(u + \frac{2c}{\gamma-1} \right) + cu \frac{1}{A} \frac{\partial A}{\partial x} &= 0 \\ \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(u - \frac{2c}{\gamma-1} \right) + (u-c) \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(u - \frac{2c}{\gamma-1} \right) - cu \frac{1}{A} \frac{\partial A}{\partial x} &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

where s is the entropy, c is the speed of sound, and A is the area. It should be noted that the reduced-order model was developed based on the governing equations written using the zeta variables as opposed to the characteristic variables. Unsteadiness was introduced to the full-order model by adding an outlet pressure oscillation of the form

$$p_{\text{out}}(t) = f(t) = \bar{p}(1 + \tilde{A} \sin(\tilde{\omega}t + \varphi)) \quad (21)$$

where the subscript ‘‘out’’ denotes values at the outlet boundary, \bar{p} is the mean static pressure at the outlet, \tilde{A} is the amplitude, $\tilde{\omega}$ is the angular velocity, and φ is the phase shift. The nozzle had an area variation of [45, p. 327]

$$A(x) = \begin{cases} 1 + 2.2(x - 0.5)^2 & 0.0 \leq x \leq 0.5 \\ 1 + 1.2223(x - 0.5)^2 & 0.5 \leq x \leq 1.0 \end{cases} \quad (22)$$

The full-order model solution was obtained using MacCormack’s technique [46]. A grid convergence study was performed, using 51, 101 and 201 grid points. The variation of the steady-state Mach number at the outlet with grid size is shown in Table 1. It is apparent that the Mach number values are converging to an asymptotic value. Since the difference between the coarse and fine mesh results were small, the coarse grid was used for the rest of the calculations.

Figure 1: Time coefficient comparisons for $\tilde{\omega} = 1$ rad/sec and $\tilde{A} = 0.02$ for the quasi-one-dimensional nozzle

Grid	Steady-State Mach Number	Change
51	0.3598	0.16%
101	0.3603	
201	0.3605	0.04%

Table 1: Steady-state outlet Mach number variation with mesh size for the quasi-one-dimensional nozzle

The full-order model solution was compared against the isentropic nozzle equations and against the numerical solution provided in Anderson [45, p. 332-3] for a steady flow. For the unsteady flows, the full-order model solution was compared to the solution obtained from the isentropic equations. Full-order model solutions were generated for 147 seconds. A total of $N=2000$ snapshots of the full-order model solutions were saved making up 8 periods.

Three test cases were used to verify the ROM: (1) $\tilde{A} = 0.02$ and $\tilde{\omega} = 1$ rad/sec, (2) $\tilde{A} = 0.02$ and $\tilde{\omega} = 2$ rad/sec, and (3) $\tilde{A} = 0.03$ and $\tilde{\omega} = 1$ rad/sec with $\bar{p} = 0.95$ and $\varphi = 0.443$ radians for all cases. For brevity, only the first test case results are shown here, since the results of the other two cases were similar. Figure 1 compares three time coefficients corresponding to the first mode of the ζ , u , and p variables: the time coefficients corresponding to the reduced-order model with and without boundary conditions imposed by the penalty method, and the “exact” time coefficients (7) obtained from the full-order model solution without solving (11) or (14). The number of modes for each variable was $n^\zeta = n^u = n^p = 2$. As shown in Fig. 1, the time coefficients of the reduced-order model without the boundary conditions imposed by the penalty method tended to stray from the “exact” time coefficients (7) as time increased. To correct this, the penalty method was used to enforce the outlet pressure oscillation. There was good agreement between the reduced-order and the full-order models once the boundary conditions were enforced, and the reduced-order model continued to extrapolate correctly beyond the end of its sampling time.

TWO-DIMENSIONAL CHANNEL FLOW

The second validation case for the ROM was a two-dimensional channel flow. The area variation in the channel was the same as that of the quasi-one-dimensional nozzle given in (23). Because of the symmetry, only half of the channel was discretized. Figure 2 shows the mesh of the computational grid of the half channel. An oscillating static

pressure boundary condition (22) was applied at the channel outlet to create an unsteady flow. For all cases \bar{p} was 98,583 Pa and φ was zero.

Figure 2: Mesh of the two-dimensional half nozzle with 129×33 grid points

The governing equations of the full-order model were solved using the finite volume method with Roe-Riemann flux splitting and Harten entropy fix [47]. The derivatives were computed using a weighted least squares with QR decomposition. Solutions were generated for three meshes: 129×33 , 257×65 , and 513×129 . Grid convergence was assessed by comparing steady-state Mach numbers at the nozzle outlet, as shown in Table 2.

Grid	Steady-State Mach Number	Change
Coarse	0.1993	0.14%
Medium	0.1996	
Fine	0.1998	0.07%

Table 2: Steady-state outlet Mach number variation with mesh size for the two-dimensional channel

Since the difference between the coarse and fine mesh results were small and the coarse grid was less computationally intensive, the coarse grid was used for the rest of calculations.

The full-order model solution was generated for 8 periods. Each period was discretized using approximately 300 time steps. Snapshots of the full-order model were saved for each time step, such that a total of 2375 snapshots were used to generate the autocorrelation matrix \mathbf{R} .

The solution of the system of ODEs with boundary conditions enforced using the penalty method was unstable for the mesh with 129×33 grid points and for coarser meshes. To obtain a stable solution, the Jacobian was altered by modifying the number of modes used in the approximation. The ROM was generated using $n^\zeta = 1$,

Figure 3: Stabilizing effect of the modified number of modes and penalty-enforced boundary conditions for a channel case with $\tilde{\omega} = 10$ rad/sec and $\tilde{A} = 0.01$: (1) “exact” solution (7), (2) ODE solution, (3) ODE solution with boundary conditions enforced with penalty method, and (4) ODE solution with boundary conditions enforced with penalty method and modified modes

$n^u = n^v = n^p = 2$ with a modified number of modes of $n^v = 1$ in the energy conservation equation. Figure 3 shows the stabilizing effect of the modified number of modes on the mode 1 pressure time coefficient.

Figure 4 shows the maximum relative error across all nodes versus time between the reconstructed solution and the FOM solution. Herein, the error was defined as the relative error between the FOM and ROM solutions, $\varepsilon = (\mathbf{Z}_{\text{FOM}} - \mathbf{Z}_{\text{ROM}})/\mathbf{Z}_{\text{FOM}}$. Because y -velocity was close to zero, a separate relative error was used, $\varepsilon_v = (\mathbf{Z}_{\text{FOM}} - \mathbf{Z}_{\text{ROM}})/(1 + \mathbf{Z}_{\text{FOM}})$. The largest maximum error occurs around 0.2% for specific volume and all velocity components.

THREE-DIMENSIONAL AXISYMMETRIC NOZZLE FLOW

The third validation case of the ROM was the flow through an axisymmetric nozzle. The nozzle had the same area variation used by Liou [48]. The total length of the nozzle

Figure 4: Maximum relative error (%) versus time for the 2D channel case with $\tilde{\omega} = 10$ [rad/sec] and $\tilde{A} = 0.01$

was 10 inches with the throat located 5 inches downstream from the inlet.

$$A = \begin{cases} \frac{7}{4} - \frac{3}{4} \cos\left(\left(2\frac{x}{l} - 1\right)\pi\right) & 0 \leq x \leq \frac{l}{2} \\ \frac{5}{4} - \frac{1}{4} \cos\left(\left(2\frac{x}{l} - 1\right)\pi\right) & \frac{l}{2} < x \leq l \end{cases}$$

The static pressure at the exit of the nozzle varied as specified in (21), where the phase angle φ was zero. The value of the mean pressure at the exit was $\bar{p} = 101,064.87$ Pa, which was 97% of the stagnation pressure at the inlet.

The FOM was solved using the same in-house Euler solver as that used for the two-dimensional channel flow. Solutions were produced for the three grids listed in Table 3.

Type	Nodes in x-direction	Nodes in circumferential direction	Nodes in yz-plane	Total number of nodes
Coarse	21	24	145	3045
Medium	41	48	553	22,673
Fine	81	96	2161	175,041

Table 3: Grids of three-dimensional axisymmetric nozzle

The medium-size grid is shown in Fig. 5. The steady-state Mach number at the nozzle outlet was used to assess whether the solution was grid independent. The results of the grid convergence study are shown in Table 4, indicating that for the grids used herein the solution was barely affected by the grid size. The medium grid was used for the rest of the calculations as a good compromise between computational cost and accuracy.

The full-order model solution was generated for 3 periods. Each period was discretized using approximately 666 time steps. Snapshots of the full-order model were saved for each time step, such that a total of 2000 snapshots were used to generate the autocorrelation matrix \mathbf{R} .

Figure 5: Medium grid of axisymmetric nozzle

Grid	Steady-State Mach Number	Change
Coarse	0.1552	3.12%
Medium	0.1600	
Fine	0.1644	2.74%

Table 4: Steady-state outlet Mach number variation with mesh size for the 3D axisymmetric nozzle

Figure 6: Maximum relative error (%) for the 3D axisymmetric nozzle case with $\tilde{\omega} = 10$ [rad/sec] and $\tilde{A} = 0.01$

Figure 7: Maximum relative error (%) for an off-reference 2D channel case with $\tilde{\omega} = 10$ [rad/sec] and $\tilde{A} = 0.015$

Like in the previous cases, the solution of the ODE system of time coefficients (11) was unstable. To obtain a stable solution, boundary conditions were enforced using the penalty method. In addition, artificial dissipation was used to dampen unstable noise. Furthermore, the Jacobian was altered by modifying the number of modes used to approximate the u velocity in the y - and z -momentum equations and in the energy conservation equation.

Three test cases were used to verify the ROM: (1) $\tilde{A} = 0.01$, $\tilde{\omega} = 10$ rad/sec, (2) $\tilde{A} = 0.01$, $\tilde{\omega} = 20$ rad/sec, and (3) $\tilde{A} = 0.02$, $\tilde{\omega} = 10$ rad/sec. These cases were generated using the three grids: coarse, medium, and fine. For conciseness, only the results for $\tilde{A} = 0.01$, $\tilde{\omega} = 10$ rad/sec are shown for the medium mesh. Furthermore, since the v and w velocities are equal, results are only shown for the former.

The reduced-order model used $n^\zeta = n^p = 1$, $n^u = 3$, $n^v = n^w = 2$ and $\nu^{\text{diss}} = (2, 0.45, 4, 4, 2)^T \times 10^{-4}$. For stability, the approximation of u velocity in the y -momentum, z -momentum, and energy equations used only two modes, *i.e.*, $n^u = 2$.

The value of artificial dissipation was determined empirically, by gradually reducing it to when the system of ODEs became unstable. The reduced-order model solution was reconstructed using (3). The reconstruction of x -velocity used only the first mode, $n^u = 1$, although three modes were kept for the solution of the ODE system in order to get a stable solution for the time coefficients. Figure 6 shows the maximum relative error versus time between the reconstructed solution and the FOM solution. Despite the addition of artificial dissipation and the use of an isentropic boundary condition on specific volume, the differences between the ROM and FOM were less than 2%.

OFF-REFERENCE CONDITIONS

In the previous sections, the ROM was used to recreate the FOM solution in order to verify accuracy. In practice, however, the ROM is needed to predict solutions beyond the snapshots generated by the FOM, that is, at off-reference conditions. Instead of using the Grassman

interpolation [20] to generate off-reference condition results, a simple interpolation was sufficient for the cases presented herein. Snapshots of flows with the same geometry but different flow parameters were combined to produce the autocorrelation matrix \mathbf{R} .

Off-reference condition results were produced for the quasi-one-dimensional nozzle, two-dimensional channel, and three-dimensional axisymmetric nozzle flows. The flow conditions were interpolated between the frequency, $\tilde{\omega}$, and amplitude, \tilde{A} , of the outlet pressure oscillation. Results are shown for only the 2D channel and 3D nozzle cases.

For the two-dimensional channel flow, solutions were generated for $\tilde{\omega} = 10$ rad/sec and $\tilde{A} = 0.01$ and 0.02 . The ROM was then used to predict the flow at $\tilde{\omega} = 10$ rad/sec and $\tilde{A} = 0.015$. Figure 7 shows the time variation of the maximum error of the reconstructed ROM solution compared to the FOM solution. It's important to note that the FOM solution with an $\tilde{\omega} = 10$ rad/sec and $\tilde{A} = 0.015$ was not used to generate snapshots for the ROM. The largest error corresponds to x -velocity, but remains less than 2%. The time-averaged errors across all nodes were 0.11%, 0.29%, 0.05%, and 0.1% for specific volume, x -velocity, y -velocity, z -velocity and pressure, respectively.

For the three-dimensional axisymmetric nozzle flow, three local solutions were generated: (1) $\tilde{\omega} = 10$ rad/sec and $\tilde{A} = 0.01$, (2) $\tilde{\omega} = 20$ rad/sec and $\tilde{A} = 0.01$, and (3) $\tilde{\omega} = 10$ rad/sec and $\tilde{A} = 0.02$. (1) and (2) were interpolated to generate an off-reference solution of $\tilde{\omega} = 15$ rad/sec and $\tilde{A} = 0.01$ while (1) and (3) were interpolated to generate an off-reference solution of $\tilde{\omega} = 10$ rad/sec and $\tilde{A} = 0.015$. Both off-reference cases used the minimization method (16) for solving the penalty parameter and (20) to calculate artificial dissipation for the velocity components.

Figure 8 shows the maximum error to a representative FOM solution versus time for the off-reference solution of $\tilde{\omega} = 15$ rad/sec and $\tilde{A} = 0.01$ using $n^\zeta = n^p = 1$, $n^u = n^v = n^w = 2$. The x -velocity had the largest error of approximately 5%, while all other variables had errors of

Figure 8: Maximum relative error (%) for an off-reference 3D axisymmetric nozzle case with $\tilde{\omega} = 15$ [rad/sec] and $\tilde{A} = 0.01$

Figure 9: Maximum relative error (%) for an off-reference 3D axisymmetric nozzle case with $\tilde{\omega} = 10$ [rad/sec] and $\tilde{A} = 0.015$

less than 1%. For this case, the time-averaged errors across all nodes were 0.13%, 1.87%, 0.06%, 0.05%, 0.05% for specific volume, x -velocity, y -velocity, z -velocity, and pressure respectively.

Figure 9 shows the time variation of the maximum error between the ROM and the FOM solutions for the off-reference solution of $\tilde{\omega} = 10$ rad/sec and $\tilde{A} = 0.015$ using $n^\zeta = n^p = 1, n^u = n^v = n^w = 3$. Again, x -velocity had the largest error of approximately 4.75% while the others errors remained approximately below 1.5%. The time-averaged errors across all nodes were 0.14%, 0.90%, 0.12%, 0.13%, and 0.05% for specific volume, x -velocity, y -velocity, z -velocity and pressure, respectively.

COMPUTATIONAL TIME

This section summarizes and compares the computational effort of the full-order and reduced-order models. Table 5 includes the averaged computational times for three cases: (1) 2D channel flow with 8,514 nodes and using 7 modes in total, (2) 3D axisymmetric nozzle with 3,045 nodes and using 9 modes in total, and (3) 3D

axisymmetric nozzle case with 22,673 nodes and using 9 modes in total. All cases had 4 runs that varied the angular velocity and amplitude of the outlet pressure oscillation, and calculated the CPU run time for their respective FOM and ROM simulations. The FOM simulation includes both steady and unsteady CPU times. This is because a steady computation was run to generate an initial solution for the unsteady run. Note also that the speedup reported did not include the CPU time needed for snapshot generation for the ROM. The speedup reported in Table 5 varied between 1.23×10^4 and 9.17×10^4 .

Case	FOM [s]	ROM [s]	Speedup $\times 10^4$
1	15,844.21	0.40	3.97
2	15,062.60	0.63	2.43
3	551,165.97	6.28	8.78

Table 5: CPU run time comparison between the ROM and the FOM

Furthermore, the run time of the zeta-variable ROM was compared to a traditional, primitive-variable ROM which uses density instead of specific volume. Table 6 presents the computational time of the two reduced-order models for the axisymmetric nozzle. The zeta-variable ROM was consistently more than four times faster than the primitive-variable ROM.

Nodes	Modes	Primitive [sec] $\times 10^{-4}$	Zeta [sec] $\times 10^{-4}$	Ratio
4257	7	5.13	1.14	4.50
16,705	7	18.40	4.34	4.25
22,673	9	36.60	7.86	4.66
66,177	7	73.10	16.20	4.51

Table 6: CPU run time comparison between the primitive-variable ROM and the zeta-variable ROM

CONCLUSIONS

A zeta-variable ROM was introduced in this paper to reduce the computational cost of full-order model unsteady flow simulations. The reduction of the computational time was the result of replacing large systems of partial differential equations, of the order of the number of unknowns of the problem, by much smaller systems of ordinary differential equations, typically on the order of tens or at most hundreds. In addition, the computational time was further reduced by using the zeta variables instead of the primitive or conservative variables, which allowed us to precompute the coefficients of the system of ordinary differential equations. Several techniques were implemented to obtain a stable solution for the system of ordinary differential equations.

This POD-based ROM was tested on three canonical flow configurations: a quasi-one-dimensional nozzle, a two-dimensional channel and a three-dimensional axisymmetric nozzle. The ROM results were compared with the FOM results at on- and off-reference conditions, and in all cases investigated a good agreement was found. Furthermore, the speedup obtained by using the zeta-variable ROM was at least 10,000 times greater than the

FOM and around 4 times greater than a primitive-variable ROM.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors would like to thank Dr. Andrew Gyekenyesi of the Ohio Aerospace Institute (OAI) for funding this project via a subcontract to OAI's Versatile Advanced Affordable Turbine Engines (VAATE) III, FA8650-14-D-2410, issued by USAF/AFMC, AFRL Wright Research Site. The authors gratefully acknowledge the computational resources provided by the Texas A&M Supercomputing Facility.

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ANNEX A

ISENTROPIC BOUNDARY CONDITION FOR SPECIFIC VOLUME

An isentropic boundary condition for specific volume at the outlet is formulated using the isentropic relations

$$\frac{p^*}{p} = \left(\frac{\rho^*}{\rho}\right)^\gamma = \left(\frac{\zeta}{\zeta^*}\right)^\gamma$$

with nondimensionalization

$$p' = \frac{p}{q_{\text{ref}}} \quad \rho' = \frac{\rho}{\rho_{\text{ref}}} \quad T' = \frac{T}{T_{\text{ref}}}$$

where ' denotes a nondimensional term. Here $q_{\text{ref}} = \rho_{\text{ref}} v_{\text{ref}}^2$ and $v_{\text{ref}} = \sqrt{\gamma R T_{\text{ref}}}$. To begin, the isentropic relations are nondimensionalized.

$$\frac{p^*}{p' q_{\text{ref}}} = \left(\frac{\rho^*}{\rho' \rho_{\text{ref}}}\right)^\gamma = \left(\frac{\zeta'}{\zeta^* \rho_{\text{ref}}}\right)^\gamma$$

At the outlet, the dimensionless pressure, p' , is oscillated with function $f(t)$.

$$\frac{p^*}{f(t) q_{\text{ref}}} = \left(\frac{\zeta'}{\zeta^* \rho_{\text{ref}}}\right)^\gamma$$

In order to put it in terms of ζ' , the powers are switched and both sides are multiplied by $\frac{\rho_{\text{ref}}}{\rho^*}$.

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{p^*}{f(t) q_{\text{ref}}}\right)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}} &= \frac{\zeta'}{\zeta^* \rho_{\text{ref}}} \\ \frac{\rho_{\text{ref}}}{\rho^*} \left(\frac{p^*}{f(t) q_{\text{ref}}}\right)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}} &= \frac{\rho_{\text{ref}}}{\rho^*} \frac{\zeta'}{\zeta^* \rho_{\text{ref}}} \\ \frac{\rho_{\text{ref}}}{\rho^*} \left(\frac{p^*}{f(t) \rho_{\text{ref}} v_{\text{ref}}^2}\right)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}} &= \zeta' \\ \frac{\rho_{\text{ref}}}{\rho^*} \left(\frac{p^*}{f(t) \rho_{\text{ref}} \gamma R T_{\text{ref}}}\right)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}} &= \zeta' \\ \frac{1}{\rho^*} \left(\frac{p^* \rho_{\text{ref}}^{\gamma-1}}{f(t) \gamma R T_{\text{ref}}}\right)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}} &= \zeta' \end{aligned}$$

The equation is further simplified by assuming that the flow behaves as an ideal gas.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{\rho^*} \left(\frac{\rho^* R T^* \rho_{\text{ref}}^{\gamma-1}}{f(t) \gamma R T_{\text{ref}}}\right)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}} &= \zeta' \\ \zeta' &= \left(\frac{1}{f(t)} \frac{T^*}{T_{\text{ref}}} \left(\frac{\rho_{\text{ref}}}{\rho^*}\right)^{\gamma-1}\right)^{\frac{1}{\gamma}} \end{aligned} \tag{A.1}$$

If the reference values correspond to the total values then (A.1) reduces to

$$\zeta' = (\gamma f(t))^{-\frac{1}{\gamma}} \tag{A.2}$$